

Anders Visit to Hell.

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While animals know by instinct how to behave in the material world they move in, (find food, shelter, mate), Man is lost with no coordinates. His world is artificial, INCONSISTENCY his essence. he assumes such separation from the world, intensifying and focusing his being to the point of making this openness a real and profound one, he compensates¹ the world (or fills in the gap) with his own self,

1st Circle: The identification of the self with HIS failure.

Being free means to be foreign; not to be made for particularly anything; to be in any horizon; To experience itself as contingent, the self is a victim of his own freedom. Therefore, the notion of contingency has two sides:

- a. the lack of ground of the self by itself
- b. its existence precisely as it is.

2nd Circle: I AM MYSELF, its forgery.

The translation of this shock: “that I am precisely myself”, in

- interrogative - theoretical level - forgery
- real: anacoluthon because >fundamental and too absurd to be answered.
- Worse: judgement or negative proposition, has no grounds.

Unmasked by underlying foundation:

I am –unfortunately- despite everything, nevertheless, myself.

Deceptively, translated as: I AM MYSELF.

The verb “**is**” as a transformation of one determination to another by an ambiguous transition, equivocal transition is the core of his analysis:

Its meaning is ungraspable due to constant change.

3rd Circle: Extension of contingency.

The awe over contingency formulated before in the statement “I am myself”, discovers now in each thing and in each place an opportunity to manifest and nourish expressing itself as: “I am not this nor that, but precisely myself”.

The world and the self, complement and intensify each other in what they have chance. If the contingent self takes advantage of the world to confirm its own contingency, the world’s contingency will be, at the same time, more radical.

This state of awe is the scope of validity of the non-contradiction principle, its pathology is that it continually destroys such frameworks, every *hoc et illud* is exactly the same.

Each determined relationship supposes the loss of every other possibility and reaches the pathological if he remains in the purely theoretical, and won’t exert his freedom practically in the constitution of his world.

¹ This “gap” is the field of freedom.

4th Circle: General validity of the Philosophic Anthropology.

Philosophy tends to consider not philosophic the not frequent many times because of the identification with the general and essential, admitting only what is verifiable as scientific. The less familiar human types, can perform interpretative roles towards the general, under the consideration of its rarity: a state of shock of the contingent is rare because:

- a) In the first place, the duplicity of the self is not praxis-experienced: man can truthfully make something of himself which afterwards is found as preexistent;
- b) In second place, because the mortal shock is solved in attitudes considered as a *modus vivendi*, attitudes which hide its contingency.

So, the fact of variation, (not the constant of variability) defines the specifically human in philosophical anthropology.

As a counter example, the nihilist who perpetuates the inconsistency and indetermination of his role

- cannot decide on any determination,
- confuses “can” with the conditional “could”
- only wishes to encounter with his most “formal” self

is an exceptional case.

5th Circle: Shame: Moral Alchemy.

The state of shock as a life’s attitude is called: shame.

Experiencing such particular shame, demands as a formal condition:

- I am capable, at the same time, to be identical and not identical with myself;
- get out of my skin and think of it differently as myself (category of strangeness);
- I can find myself experiencing freedom but –not being free-.

Shame is not born from this incoherence (which is a consequence), it is originally unravelling.

What starts as shame ends as honor: He who feels shames returns to himself. To be able to do this: do not stay adrift at the mercy of the world, to link the heritage of “being precisely myself, and also “be of the world” and come back to one’s self is the testimony of man’s double condition.

The ashamed is proud of his hiding, he sublimates his shame and falsifies his true motive which was the scandal of shame, of the identification failure. He turns shame into a virtue. The concealment mends the hidden by its secrecy, or better still, it keeps it as his most intimate and implicit self: that which belongs to me and only to myself. This concealment appropriates of what is hidden, of what the world is, what is “common” with the world, in such a way that is now private and own. These hidden motives are now the occasion, the consolidation of one’s self, a true reason of pride. The one that transforms shame in this way, commits no longer to the world but only to himself, and abstaining of it with resistance and purity, denies the fact that he has come to the world as a contingent being and the imposture of worldliness.

This antinomy has become a *modus vivendi*, the thousand ways of hypocrisy, disguise, and comedy, provisionally he may abandon his particular existence, take another form and make himself, the matter and occasion, of multiple personifications.

The provisional is conclusive: among all species, the human one, is most lacking of attributes.

Sixth Circle. The perfect future: Man in subjunctive.

In shame, Man discovers himself, as a being who was there before he experienced himself.

- The imperfect tense “I was there” is in a way a sort of denial of me as a free being;
- the past perfect tense to which it can be further traced, indicates “that which was there” is not me.

The freedom, that doubts continues to the past perfect scope:

- pretending to reach what is below opens the possibility to a perfect future.
 - This possibility is a sign of
 - a. freedom
 - b. non-freedom .

The future is indeterminate.

(Philosophies from Hegel to Heidegger, come from Kant’s theory of time)

The core is, that if man does not realize this freedom practically, using the dimension of future to go over his contingent `being-precisely-now, at this crucial moment, he consumes his time with his hands tied, and **commits to the indefinite ad infinitum**, he compromises his freedom in vain.

The more he moves, abandoning his bonds in the direction this so-called freedom unveils, the more he gets lost in the indeterminate reign.

- time and space neutralizations, can be identified as the **nihilist panic in the freedom paradox**:
 - “never wanting to be precisely me, and nevertheless
 - “having to be precisely myself” perpetually.

7th Circle: Thirst for power and glory.

The self, sick of time and space, wants to neutralize the contingency of the place where he is:

- he wants to be everywhere, simultaneously, and seize it all at once.
- The desire of possession is only the specification of a deep thirst for power.
- Constrain the world into himself, the world, can become mine
- instead of becoming I,
is the first scandal and the first objective for the thirst for power.
- Absolute deception: if the world stays the same...,
(Echo of Nietzsche’s aphorism: “If God existed how could I bear not being him?”)

In his thirst for power, because he is not everything, then from here on

- he must *have* everything: appropriating and representing it;
- being everywhere, omnipresent.
- his actual and incomplete state can be seen, as the *phenomenon* in regard, to the *idea*: To this glorious statue, he is only a true and temporary copy,

- the paradox: the more his glory increases, the less related is the statue to “himself”
The statue has usurped his name and will get the glory in his stead for a long time, even after his death.
Overwhelmed and despondent, he remains envious of its big name.

The “Pathology of Freedom”:

- With philosophic exaggerations as a method, describes different ailments of this disease.
- These pathologies represent radical dangers for men of our time, we all know them, even more than we like to, here we have taken them to catastrophic off limits, compromising life itself.
- The forms of shame, disgust, desire of glory are familiar to all.
- if we do not habitually discern its contingency it is because they appear ambivalent, masked with positive aspects, they shelter the threat of the contingent, and could lead to suicidal, *modi vivendi*.
- Shame, disgust and the desire of glory take place in contingent life, therefore, as practical life is an affirmation of the self, they represent commitments to a life woven in contingency, they represent protests and insults, the dark side we all share.

BUT

- ✓ antinomies are not stronger than the love for life.
- ✓ WE Nihilists also want to live.

**SO, WE HALL RISE
COMING UP**

6th Circle Up: Life goes on.

The man who leaps from contingency to contingency losing himself in each and every one, continues with his life anyway.

He surrenders to swim his life through this intermittent swirls but sticking his head out to maintain his course. The paradox consists in that these swirls repeat and repeat along his life, -there is no before or after- but waters always reach their natural level, no matter how turbulent, because it is contained in a life. The paradox is that these “*Καοο*” sticks out the internal harmony by which the self is carved.

- a) Paradox 1 >swirl - antinomy
- b) Paradox 2 > iteration inside a life

It is by fighting the confusion and facing the impossible that Man is tempered, and by succeeding he gets to know what he is made of.

Paradox is neutral it is life that takes place in time, life goes on despite all paradox paradox is experienced as an obstacle. It is not the paradox itself that is repeated but life that makes us re-experience the paradoxical, and its above its outcome that life goes on: it is felt as a specific negation of life during a time lapse. As iteration of the identical, iteration is the beginning of the neutralization of historic time inside a life that can -even out of history- follow its course.

Man, deeply committed with the idea of antinomy, turns non-historic. That is, what he is and what he was, does not represent strictly a life; deep down, it is nothing but an event that happens by accident; that in relation to the constancy of paradox rests in the scope of the possible so, it cannot be remembered.

The contingency shock destroys then, the strict possibility of experience itself, the fact of appropriating the life lived *de facto*.

The paradox determines Man.

Life must to be first experienced (lived with the senses) and then remembered (internal senses).

Is the historic man a contingency fugitive? NO. He is beyond contingency because he knows the drill.

5th Circle Up: "I remember ergo I am".

Am I a preset Harmony?

-Nihilist: I am precisely myself > expresses my parts do not match>broken self parts must be assembled afterwards with the help of the memory

The antinomy is not seen by the memory (nor the id difficulties)

Memory accomplishes minimum ID: I remember therefore, I am myself.

The fragments of life are bits and pieces they must go into a rearrangement process.

4th Circle Up: Identification and Possessive.

What does one remember? For philosophical anthropology, is a decisive question.

Unlike perception which has its object in front: a fragment of the world, the memory is about a situation in which the one who perceives and what is perceived, the I and the world, are fused to the point that neither can be separated of this single element.

It is not the (formal) self which arranges the memory, the memory warns the self, but the lived experiences that arrange the self.

It is the experience what determines the self.

This is about life as a totality, not only the remembered fragments, life in the biographical sense. Life appears as a means, thanks to the multiple beings and to the things experimented, I own my life as myself.

I am my life=the self is life

I=is=am >MINE

the possessor + the possessed >< I belong to my life = my life belongs to me.

3rd Circle Up: I is tomorrow's LIFE.

As the I reassembles the bits and pieces kept by his memory he builds himself, a formal I, which is the face of the historic man to life, (which shelters the world). It is the vanguard of life's plenitude, willing and open to all possibilities.

Today is I, tomorrow life added with whatever comes up, and part of my life today is my yesterday's I.

Man cannot digest all at once because of its discursive nature.

The mental order compounded by different time lapses and perceptions cures Anders' despair. This clarification –legacy to the world- makes him understand his many sufferings were unnecessary.

The conception of the I as a constituent element of life, (as a moment, in a logic and temporal sense) shall not be understood as if there were no difference between both forms of life of the I (nihilistic and historic). These are, one and the same in the memory, nevertheless memory itself is not a difference, but a perpetual identification. A certain duality is obvious. A sort of gap, that life risks between herself and the I, because when it conforms the I, it is not the moment in which it outdistances in the freedom of its possibilities or when it wants to be updated. This gap always disappears in the memory, and identity is reestablished.

Life and I are melted together as only the possessive pronoun can describe.

2nd Circle Up: Stable ID

Man's self, intertwines the natural and artificial worlds: social and economic, ways and laws.

This can find balance and lead to stable situations where he is comfortable, which demonstrates he is not made for the natural world.

because the ID of the I is correlative to his world.

The roles doctor, judge, teacher... and the I being the substratum: there is no antinomy between the man and his role, especially in an ever changing world.

The world is not exterior, which manifests the futility of the terror of contingency and its assimilation through memory.

Then is there no need of identification?

Yes there is.

Man must adapt and answer to the requirements the world calls for:

MORAL and RESPONSIBLE ACTS> answer to the world about them

They only become historic, when all the above elements become vague and confused and Man is bound to be called by his name to answer about them with his identity and get back in himself.

When he answers his own call, and when he uses his own name he encounters and comes back to himself. Seen from a stable situation, the historic man reminds the baron Münchhausen who comes out of a swamp by pulling his own hair up.

If the essence of Man is not fixed, by his multiple incarnations

- a) The nihilist incarnates inconsistency (contingency) and thus determines himself
- b) The historic man is up to the task and adjusts to his *fatum*,

c) He turns the contingent a posteriori into rational in him.

1st Circle: Earthly Surface: LIFE AS AN OPEN FIELD.

The identification process is not so simple.

Without the world, the identification is not possible.

- ACTION
- ABSTRACTION OF SOCIAL ID
- NO FEAR OF CONTINGENCY
- ASSIMILATED PAST
- OWN TASK

WILL

That the world appears contingent to he who wants to modify it, is possible, but it is out of all contingency the it is HE who wants, and has the will to transform it.

To conquer an effective identification

- not in the nihilist's: "I am myself"
- nor the historic self's: "I am who I was",
- but in: **"What I wanted, I want"**.
- The constant is already in the concept of **"task"**, NOT a memory or experience, because the tasks only disappear when accomplished.

The self-identification through *Aufklärung* and the critic are for Kant an action; For him is not about ascertaining what reason is (which for him is equivalent to Man), but to build it through a critical action.

Kant's objectives are Anders' and have a further reach of what was thought at first.

Philosophic anthropology and its problem of the definition of man, should be considered, facing human action, as a productive misunderstanding and should be ended.

"What I am in an authentic sense", "What I discover in me", is always decided either by me or by somebody else.

Action, effectively, by which man is continuously defined, and determines what he is in each occasion. In this perpetual definition of himself that man offers with his actions, it is useless to appeal to the order principle and demand a short stop to raise the questions of an 'authentic' definition and establish who is man is an 'authentic' sense.

The question of knowing who am I, is not one of those to be considered but answered.